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Enhancing data sovereignty to improve intelligent mobility services in smart cities

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ABSTRACT

Smart cities aim to provide more digitalized, equitable, sustainable, and liveable cities. In smart cities data evolves as an important asset and citizens data in particular is being used to provide data-driven mobility services. Likewise, in smart cities data is produced and used by individuals having no ownership or control over these data thus affecting their security and privacy. Also, actors such as mobility service providers, companies, third parties, etc. often leverage individuals' data without regarding users' autonomy. Accordingly, data sovereignty which entails the possibility to govern and keep control over owned data is gaining widespread attention. As a result, stakeholders in the mobility sector need to share data whilst keeping control to manage data access and usage. Although, existing initiatives are promoting sovereign participation using a federated infrastructure. However, achieving an effective governance usage control and access mechanisms can be challenging especially in the transportation sector. It is thus imperative for individuals to have control, ownership, and custody over their data. This has necessitated the notions of data sovereignty. Therefore, this article employs a systematic review to examine how data sovereignty can be achieved for individuals when they use urban mobility services in smart cities by enabling the secure sharing of data by giving control of data over to individuals. Additionally, this article designs a data control scheme that can be applied to realize data sovereign mobility services. Evidence from this study provides technical and non-technical requirements needed in realizing data sovereignty in smart cities.

1. Introduction

Smart cities deploy Information and Communication Technologies (ICTs) for urban development to enable efficient use of resources, for a better quality of life, and sustainable economic development (Cuno, Bruns, Tcholtchev, Lämmel, & Schieferdecker, 2019; Anthony Jnr, 2022). In smart cities data has become an important asset by which value can be generated to better fulfill societal needs (König, 2021; Yuming, 2021; Jansen et al., 2023). For businesses such as mobility service providers data is considered as an asset that can help to generate revenue (Kaulgud, 2022). As such smart cities are employing data from different stakeholders across the data ecosystem which comprises of companies, citizens, municipalities, etc., who collaborates to ensures that data can be made available, accessible, and usable for the society at large (Cuno et al., 2019). Data ecosystems involve the integration of distributed data sources from different stakeholders. Fundamentally, it provides the basis for data-driven business models which relies on the availability and accessibility of heterogeneous data sources from

different stakeholders for added value creation (Lohmöller et al., 2022). Smart cities are now adopting innovation processes to improve or design novel data driven services that generate value for the society based on data collected from the citizens (König, 2021; Anthony Jr, 2023a). To this end, stakeholders such as mobility service providers can extract and synthesize value from data for providing intelligent mobility services such as smart traffic management, traffic flow optimization, shared mobility services, etc. (Cuno et al., 2019; Jnr, 2024c).

Intelligent mobility services contribute towards cities achieving sustainable urban mobility. Accordingly, urban mobility has become an important area for the deployment of new innovations as it is essential to ensure seamless and efficient transportation of human and goods (Jnr, 2024a). Thus, there is need for newer data driven urban mobility approaches that supports the sustainable governance and operation to enhance sustainable urban mobility in smart cities. As such the pursuit of developing advanced intelligent mobility solutions remains an ongoing development (Tan, 2023). Additionally, the use of data to ensure intelligent mobility services has become important in smart cities, due to chal-

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lenges such as unclear data control, ownership, uncertainty in data access and sharing (Yuming, 2021). Similarly, it is important to safeguard privacy and individual control when sharing data (König, 2021). Therefore, in smart cities there is need for data owners and data providers who provide data to have control and access to their data (Holfelder et al., 2022). This necessitates data sovereignty in smart cities (Yuming, 2021). Presently, in smart cities there are many data sharing platforms that facilitate the sharing of data, but these approaches are faced with different challenges such as the difficulty in assigning rights, fair pricing, inadequate security, difficulty in complying with usage rules, and inadequate data protection laws.

In smart cities this has resulted to low participation among data owners and data producers who are not willingness to share their data across different data ecosystem (Tao, Yang, & Ge, 2022). In Europe polices such as The General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) have been initiated to protect residents' data rights and privacy. However as pointed out by Scheider, Lauf, Möller, & Otto, 2023 the GDPR entirely ignores the economic interests of residents and further hinders fair distribution and systematic generation of financial gain as related to individuals' personal data. Also, the GDPR is limited in accelerating data-driven business models and innovation in smart cities. Furthermore, existing data ecosystems in the literature includes initiatives such as the International Data Spaces Association (IDSA) (Otto, Steinbuss, Teuscher, & Lohmann, 2019), and GAIA-X (Gaia-X Technical Committee, 2021), which both aims to provide a reliable digital environment for the discovery, processing, and sharing of available data, across specific domains. However, these data ecosystems are faced with challenges in establishing trust needed among participants in smart cities as the current process is heavily dependent on organizational agreements and procedures. The participating stakeholders receive no security guarantees to verify that other participants handle and use their shared data as initially intended.

Currently, there are several discussions on data sovereignty found in the literature, but studies that investigated data sovereignty from the lens of intelligent mobility services or public transportation is limited. Thus, there is need to develop fair, trusted, and transparent data ecosystems that enable actors to exercise control over their data to allows increased mutual benefit from mobility data to support intelligent mobility services in smart cities. Thus, the lack of a credible guarantees essentially ends the data sovereignty of participants involved in data sharing within smart cities (Lohmöller et al., 2022). To that end, research on data sovereignty is urgently required to investigate how to ensure that individuals have total control over their data being used in smart cities. To address these issues this study examines the following research questions.

- What are the benefits of enhancing data sovereignty in data sharing eco-systems across smart cities?
- What practices are applied to realize data sovereign mobility services in smart cities?
- What are the requirements needed in realizing data sovereignty for intelligent mobility services in smart cities?
- How can entities exercise control over their data to support intelligent mobility services in smart cities?

Therefore, the main objective of this study is to contributes to current discussions of data sovereignty towards developing fair data ecosystems where individuals are actively involved in smart cities. Accordingly, a data control scheme is developed in this study to facilitate data sovereignty for citizens and businesses (mobility service providers), by providing access to reliable and quality data that inform urban mobility development. Additionally, the data control scheme can enable intelligent mobility services such as improved public transportation services, optimized route planning, and reduced congestion. Thus, this article explores how individuals can be given full control and autonomy over the governance of their own data to improve intelligent mobility services in the context of public transportation in smart cities. Additionally, evidence from this study also identify the key requirements (both technical

and non-technical) needed to achieve data sovereignty in smart cities. The structure of this article is organized as follows. Section 2 is literature review. Section 3 presents the methodology and Section 4 is the respective findings. Section 5 details the discussion, recommendations, and implication. Section 6 is the conclusion.

2. Literature review

2.1. Background of data sovereignty

Data sovereignty relates to data rights and ownership identification which in recent years has increasingly become a key concern for individuals, enterprises, and nations due to challenges such as issues in data sharing and usage, unclear data ownership, and personal information leakage (Lohmöller et al., 2022). Data sovereignty is emerging as a critical concern for individuals, businesses, and government (Yuming, 2021). The claim of data sovereignty is intrinsically linked to employing the legal tools and policies in the hands of individuals in the data ecosystem, supporting use of contract to ensure that data exchange and usage is in compliance with specific and general regulations, ranging from GDPR to anti-trust and cyber-security regulations (Duisberg, 2022). Accordingly, data sovereignty refers to the fact that data is subject to the regulations and laws of the region (e.g. EU) or country in which it is generated, stored or located. It establishes the right of individuals and businesses to have right over their data, including how the data is accessed, processed, stored, and shared (Frick, 2023). Data sovereignty also relates to adhering to compliance with specific and general regulations, such as cyber-security regulations and anti-trust to GDPR. Data sovereignty ensures data rights of data owners and data providers are preserved and ownership of the data is identifiable. Accordingly in data ecosystems data sovereignty relates to ownership and control of data in relation to specific claims and obligations made by involved participants (data owners/data producers and data users/data consumers) (Lohmöller et al., 2022). Data sovereignty broadens to the interest of territories in the integrity, sanctity, and security of data and of the values, cultural and other contextual norms associated with data (Oguamanam, 2020).

Presently most individuals are not aware of the data that is being collected concerning them (Hummel, Braun, & Dabrock, 2021b). Data sovereignty aims ascertain that individuals need to know what data is collected about them, where and how their data being used. Hummel et al. (2021b) affirmed that data sovereignty ensures that information stored digitally is subject to the customs and practices of the nation in which it is localized (geolocation of data), thus enabling the country to store and govern its own data. Hummel, Braun, Tretter, and Dabrock (2021a) added that data sovereignty involves rules governing where certain data sets such as citizens and government data should be stored within confined national boundaries. Data sovereignty is a part of digital sovereignty, and it involves keeping control over data for both economic and political reasons. Data sovereignty refers to the capability of an entity (including a citizen and a company) of being completely self-determined with respect to its data (Yang, Guo, Yu, & Zhang, 2022). Tao et al. (2022) maintained that data sovereignty entails finding a balance between the need to share data with others and the need to safeguard personal data. It is the self-determination of entities regarding the use of their data based on data usage agreements (Altendeitering, Pampus, Larrinaga, Legaristi, & Howar, 2022). Data sovereignty assess if entities can exercise full control over the use of their personal data. Data sovereignty improves the controllability of individuals and businesses in having access to their data by determining who is permitted to use their data. This also involves specifying the conditions under which their data are accessed and processing (Hummel et al., 2021b).

Conclusively, data sovereignty is the ability of individuals to self-regulate at any time and preferences which actors, systems, and infrastructures can use their (personal) data for designated purposes (Lauf et al., 2022). Researchers such as Yaodong & Shuai, 2022 re-

ferred to data sovereignty as finding a balance in sharing data and also protecting personal data. Data sovereignty provide data owners with the capabilities to strict govern data usage by setting rules with clear and enforceable usage rights attached across the life cycle of the data. Hummel et al. (2021a) argued that data sovereignty pertains to the empowerment of individuals and businesses in terms of their data. It involves individuals making self-determined and independent decisions regarding what happens to their data. It involves individuals having knowledge of who can gain access to their data and where such data is being transferred and used by third parties. Moreover, it enables individuals to be able to access, view, save, track, update, and delete their personal data (Lauf et al., 2022).

Furthermore, Boye, Matar, and Neuschwander (2023) defined data sovereignty as the ability to make decisions about the use of data collected in regard to one's own asset. In a national context data sovereignty relates to the management, authority, and governance of data by states through the initiation of regulations, policies, and laws to guide the creation and flow of personal and non-personal data within the jurisdiction of the country for strategic and economic interests, as well as for national security. Data sovereignty ensures that a nation's data is not utilized for external/private companies' profit but for improving domestic economic growth and public services (Kaulgud, 2022). Thus, data sovereignty has become central as many countries especially in Europe are enthusiastically engage in repossessing the governance of their digital space from tech companies due to the political and economic benefits of data (Matambo & Ugar, 2022). For data sovereignty to be achieved in smart cities, data owners and data providers could indicate that the data is only to be used for a certain period of time and afterwards deleted (Altendeitering et al., 2022). This is important as there have been loss of control over citizens data which has resulted to considerable challenge, making it demanding to safeguard data privacy (Hummel et al., 2021a).

2.2. Data sovereignty implementation in smart cities

Presently, there are several discussions on data sovereignty in smart cities or urban context found in the literature. Among these studies Alizadeh, Dutia, & Clements, 2024 researched on smart Barcelona and identified the gap between lackluster implementation and inspiring rhetoric in transformative approaches. Fernandez-Monge et al. (2024) explored how to reclaim data towards improving urban governance in Barcelona by investigating the key goals and instruments adopted by municipalities to limit corporate control of city data. Foth, Anastasiu, Mann, and Mitchell (2021) investigated data collection/automation in smart cities to achieve a citizen and community developments in Barcelona and Toronto based on a model (DataCare) offered to communities, citizens, and businesses to increase data autonomy and transparency. Herian (2020) investigated the adoption of Blockchain, adhering of GDPR, and data sovereignty (taking control), from a psycho-political framework perspective for technology users.

Similarly, Lynch (2020) examined the important discourses and experimental strategies of a local movement centered on claiming technological sovereignty in Barcelona focused on digitalization and smart city. Furthermore, Mann, Mitchell, Foth, and Anastasiu (2020) explored technological sovereignty as related to anxieties of control within digital urban contexts to provide significant social license for smart cities in Barcelona. Veale (2020) examined sovereignty, privacy preserving, and contact tracing protocols based on a developed decentralized open protocol and codebase. Additionally, Couture and Toupin (2019)) explored the notion of sovereignty as related to the digital sphere from a governmental policy perspective. Bratton (2016) studied sovereignty from a software perspective in different areas such as in smart grids, mobile apps, cloud platforms, smart cities, and internet of things highlighting the need for employing a stacks approach.

Although studies which explored data sovereignty in smart cities (e.g. Lynch, 2020; Mann et al., 2020; Foth et al., 2021), exists research that investigated data sovereignty from the lens of intelligent mobil-

ity services or public transportation is limited. Thus, there is need to develop fair, trusted, and transparent data ecosystems that enable actors to exercise control over their data to allows increased mutual benefit from mobility data to support intelligent mobility services in smart cities. Such data ecosystems can allow data owners and data producers to incentivize their data minimizing power concentration by multinational corporations. An approach that supports fairness, trust, and transparency that facilitates secure data flows through a harmonized, open data ecosystem built around strong regulations and policies such as "the European Data Governance Act" and "the Data Act" is needed to support discoverability and access to data (Montero-Pascual, Finger, & De Abreu Duarte, 2023).

3. Methodology

This study investigates how data sovereignty can support intelligent mobility services in smart cities based on a systematic literature review (SLR). SLR is a review of existing literature employed in a methodical way (Maybury, Corcoran, & Cipcigan, 2022). SLR is adopted in this study as a method to ensure that this study is extensive and that all pertinent research published within the field are included. Similar to prior studies (Maybury et al., 2022; Anthony Jr, 2023a), in this study SLR was executed based on the method outlined by Kitchenham (2004). A search of relevant literatures was carried out using online databases (Google Scholar, Scopus, and Web of Science). The search string was formulated which comprises of specific terms combined with the Boolean operator "AND" and "OR". The search keywords include: "data sovereignty" or "smart cities" or "intelligent mobility services" or "smart mobility" or "urban mobility" and "data usage control *" and "data access mechanisms **", and "data-driven mobility services" or "data sovereign mobility services" and "public transportation*" and "technical requirements *" and "non-technical requirements *". The selection process employed for the SLR is shown in Fig. 1.

As seen Fig. 1 a total of 154 sources were retrieved from the online databases. After which a duplicate check was employed, and 31 sources were deleted resulting to 123 sources. Then 50 sources were removed based on the title not fully supporting the study area, resulting to 73 sources. Next, 5 sources were removed as the abstract was not related to

Fig. 1. Studies search process used in this study.

data sovereignty in smart cities. Additionally, 9 sources were excluded as the content of the sources was not related to data sovereign mobility services resulting to 59 sources. Lastly, 16 sources were added via snowballing and cross referencing to strengthen the literature resulting to a total of 75 sources. Then secondary data was extracted, and descriptive analysis was carryout to present findings related to the research questions. For inclusion and exclusion criteria, this study is more focuses on sources published in English language such as journals, conference proceedings, chapters of books, and technical reports. Also, only studies published from 2010 till date (2024) were considered in this study. Sources that provide evidence on data sovereignty in smart cities were screened and if the source was found to be scientifically sound it was included. Additionally, if the aim, objectives, and research problem(s) were well described such sources were included. Studies published in other languages other than English language were excluded. Lastly, this study included technical reports on data strategies from the European Commission (EC).

4. Findings

The section presents the main outcomes based on the research questions being examined. To descriptively present the findings from the selected sources a thorough analysis was descriptively carried to present findings on data sovereignty from a national perspective, dataspace for data exchange in smart cities, data sovereignty from a national perspective, and data sovereignty from industrial perspective. More importantly findings are provided on data sovereignty for intelligent mobility services in smart cities, data-driven mobility services in smart cities, data governance of intelligent mobility services in smart cities, and technical and non-technical requirements for data sovereignty.

4.1. Data sovereignty from a national perspective

Data in digital form is created, collected, and shared across the world to support primary societal functions, including energy systems, commerce, healthcare, national security, education, transportation, etc. Governments across the world are now considering data as a valuable asset. As such the flow of data need to be regulated and governed in a manner that benefits citizens and businesses in a country (Kaulgud, 2022). Due to the fact that individuals' data is being collected and managed by a few multi-national corporations such as Google, Facebook, Amazon, Microsoft, Apple, etc. Several nations are now drafting polices that enables individuals to manage the life cycle of their data. Policymakers consider sovereignty as having self-governance over data generated in their territory or jurisdiction (Jarke, 2020). Nationally, sovereignty refers to the autonomous right of each nation to regulate data that is generated within its borders (Kaulgud, 2022). In national context sovereignty involves claims to autonomy and control that are linked to technologies, data, and infrastructures. Hence the possibility of having control over one's data assets is often termed as data sovereignty (Hellmeier et al., 2023).

For example, "data localization" or "data residency" policies in some countries require businesses to keep certain types of data within the jurisdiction or country of origin, by placing considerable restrictions on data transmission outside the state of origin (Oguamanam (2020); Hummel et al. (2021a)). For instance, in Germany the government requires that confidential data of German companies and their workforce never leave German territory and only German citizens are permitted to administer the storage of those data (Esposito et al., 2018), to maintain data sovereignty. In the United States of America (USA) data sovereignty can be traced back to the US Patriot Act in 2001, which gives the US Government right to access data saved on servers located within the USA (Hellmeier et al., 2023). Moreover, initiatives such as the "Data Governance Act" and the "European Strategy for Data" are being proposed to foster data ownership within the data-driven economy (Calzada, 2021).

4.2. Dataspace for data exchange in smart cities

As previously stated smart cities are cities that use advanced ICTs to achieve intelligent, efficient, and sustainable urban operations such as intelligent mobility services (Nigon, Glize, Dupas, Crasnier, & Boes, 2016; Cuno et al., 2019; Anthony Jnr, 2022; Yao, 2024). Smart cities leverage diverse technologies to enable the utilization of data towards modernization of cities to improve the quality of life of citizens (Jain, Gue, & Jain, 2023; Yan, Jiang, Huang, Zhang, & Zhou, 2023; Bokolo, 2023b). To improve cities into smarter cities, in 2020 the European Commission (EC) launched its European data strategy, aimed at transforming the European Union (EU) into an international leader for data-driven society (Montero-Pascual et al., 2023). To further contribute towards the European strategy for data (digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/policies/strategy-data), the EC initiated a common European data space (digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/policies/data-space), as part of the strategic data spaces. The suggested data spaces comprise of agriculture, health, manufacturing, Green Deal, mobility, energy, media, finance, tourism, public administration, skills, and cultural heritage (Ducuing, Benmayor, & Dheu, 2022). A major goal of the EC's mobility strategy and action plan is the boosting of innovation in data and Artificial Intelligence, which is a crucial part of the European mobility towards fostering a common European mobility data space (Ducuing, Benmayor, & Dheu, 2022).

Furthermore, as part of the common European data space, the mobility data space (digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/policies/mobility-data), was proposed by the EC to enable data flow among actors towards improving mobility in the EU to develop the single transport area with respect to European values. However, for the European mobility data space to support public transportation it should be able to connect existing and emergent data initiatives, in addition to local and national data spaces (Montero-Pascual et al., 2023). This can support for reinforcing data discoverability, enhancing interoperability, and accelerating the emergence of innovative data ecosystems covering all public transportation modes and micro-mobility services across cities and national access points in Europe (Montero-Pascual et al., 2023; Anthony Jr, 2023a, 2023b). The European mobility data space could support fair, transparent, trusted, sovereign data exchange among different actors such as data owners, data providers, data brokers, data intermediaries, data consumers, data users, digital platforms, identity services providers, and many others. It contributes to existing polices as defined particularly in the European Data Governance Act (digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/policies/data-governance-act), the eFTI Regulation, ITS Directive, and many other modal legislations as well as in the Data Act (digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/policies/data-act) (Montero-Pascual et al., 2023). For cities to become digitalized, resilient, and sustainable as seen in Fig. 2, municipalities must govern the sovereign use of data.

Fig. 2 conceptualize the overall goal of intelligent mobility services in smart cities. These goals are further contributing to efficiency by prioritizing non-motorized transport networks, creating optimized, dense, mixed-use networks of streets and paths that co-locate demand and supply centers, and safety towards vision zero by transiting safety and lower transit-related injury and mortality, and finally improving public health and quality of life. Therefore, to support the actualization of a sustainable, digitalized and resilient intelligent mobility services in smart cities a set of platforms is required that will support cities in exercising control over their data to support the data exchange via data ecosystems in order to become a data driven intelligent urban environment. One such platforms is the notion of a "data space" (Cuno et al., 2019) proposed by the EC (Montero-Pascual et al., 2023), analogous to the common European data space which is part of the European data strategy (Larrinaga, 2022; Montero-Pascual et al., 2023). One of the objectives of European data strategy is to propose initiatives to build common European data spaces, that facilitates the accessibility, availability, pooling, and sharing of data (Montero-Pascual et al., 2023).

Fig. 2. Key goals of intelligent mobility services in smart cities.

The term “data space” is still recent (Montero-Pascual et al., 2023). In smart cities, *data spaces* are important as they contribute to the goal of the “European data economy”. Data spaces further facilitate the evolution of data ecosystems (Anthony Jr, 2023b). As such in April 2018, the EC introduced a strategic report “Building a European Data Economy” (European Commission; and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions, 2017). The EC emphasized that data spaces are vital the development of the data economy. In its statement, the EU referred to the “European Data Space” as a seamless digital domain that facilitates the development of new data-driven products and services (European Commission, 2018). In the context of this study a *mobility data space* is not typically a mobility database or a hardware infrastructure. But can be seen as a framework for federating and inter-linking different public transportation data ecosystems that are relatively heterogeneous, silos, and often difficult to access or discover (Ducuing, Benmayor, & Dheu, 2022).

4.2.1. Trust and transparency in data-sharing for intelligent mobility services

Generally, the actualization of intelligent mobility services in smart cities requires a trusted, transparent, and secured data exchanges that can help foster data sovereignty for different actors especially for data owners and data producers. Also, there are issues related to the labor and effort involved in dealing with data governance issues such as privacy and ownership as the most stakeholders (data owners, data producers, data users, and data consumers), do not have time to tackle this issues since stakeholders are concerned with payment model for having to deal with preference settings, checking up on data, reporting, monitoring etc. as regards to the usage and sharing of their data. Thus, to ease the exchange and re-use of data within the EU, member states are obliged to set up National Access Points (NAPs). The NAP is used by transport authorities, transport operators, infrastructure managers (railway) and mobility on demand service providers to provide their real-time traffic data, historic traffic data, and static travel data. Example of data that can be shared via the NAP comprise for instance trip plans, location searches (origin and destination), trip plan computation, routes/lines, network topology for (railway) infrastructure managers to provide, etc.

In transportation sector such as the railway sector, data should be provided employing the standards and technical specifications defined in the Technology Access Program (TAP) and The Technical Specifications for Interoperability (TSI). TAP supports interoperability via an open-source licensing for interface formats. Similarly, TSI specifies the operational and technical standards that should be met by part of subsystem or each subsystem in order to meet the important requirements thereby ensuring the interoperability of the railway system in the EU. The data is expected to be provided with their associated metadata. Using Application Programming Interface (APIs) that grant access to data via the NAP which is to be publicly available allowing different actors to register to gain access (Ducuing, Benmayor, & Dheu, 2022).

However, there is need for individuals to exercise control when they share their data to support intelligent mobility services in smart cities (Ducuing, Benmayor, & Dheu, 2022). Thus, there is need for an open data ecosystem that supports data sovereignty by enabling trustworthy, and secure control of data exchange between data owners, data providers, data brokers, data intermediaries, data consumers, data users, digital platforms, identity services providers, etc.

4.3. Data sovereignty for intelligent mobility services in smart cities

Digitalization has notably impacted the society and how organizations conduct business. This development has resulted to the generation of data produced by citizens and organizations (Jnr, 2024a). With data becoming an enabler for public value and driver for new socioeconomic invention. Data has changed the way by which individuals, users, businesses, or institutions carryout their daily activities (Sheikh, Foth, & Mitchell, 2023). The concept of a smart city is closely linked to the use of data as a resource to create value added services for citizens (Jnr, 2024b). In smart cities intelligent mobility services adopt digital technologies to better serve people’s transportation needs while achieving sustainable mobility with a focus on sustainability of the environment and society (Tan, 2023). As citizens use intelligent mobility services connected to data ecosystems provided by mobility service providers there is need to provide strong and continual assurances about the security of data provided to maintain each individual’s data sovereignty. To support data privacy of individuals regulations are formulated, such as the European Union (EU) General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). This type of regulations focuses on upholding national data sovereignty towards the actualization of digital and technological sovereignty which helps to protect individual and business data (Hellmeier & von Scherenberg, 2023).

Accordingly, over the years different approaches have been proposed that aim to promote data sovereignty ideas. One of the fewer studies in this area is the work presented by the German government to support the European mobility data space towards the development and implementation of specific data spaces for the mobility and automotive sector. One of the use cases from the mobility data space is the industry-based Catena-X automotive network which developed a data space as an integral and central component to facilitate a data driven value chain Larrinaga, (2022). Moreover, Catena-X provides a solution that enables one-to-one secure data exchange between different actors within the network based on the industrial data space connector. Also, the eclipse data space connector was also used in certain use cases within Catena-X as the main link that allow for exchanging data securely across different organizations. Another notable contribution from the literature is the mobility data space (mobility-dataspace.eu) developed by GAIA-X (gaiax.eu), that provided a provider-neutral and interconnected data infrastructure that enables secure storage, self-governing data sharing. GAIA-X supports the use of services via a collaborative and self-sufficient data

sharing (Larrinaga, 2022). This enables all participants within the data ecosystem to determine where data is to be stored, for what purpose it is being processed for and by which actors. GAIA-X also supports the potential for businesses to deploy marketplace for monetizing data within the manufacturing value networks. This also provide incentives for data owners and data producers who share their data (Larrinaga, 2022).

Another prominent work is the initiative by the International Data Spaces (IDS), which aimed to develop data ecosystem and data spaces based on a reference architecture towards enabling sovereign data transfers using different components such as the IDS connectors (Otto, Steinbuss, Teuscher, & Lohmann, 2019). In addition, EONA-X (eona-x.eu), provided a dedicated European data space for transport, mobility, and tourism, established as part of the Gaia-X initiative. EONA-X aimed to transform the way data is exchanged and used in the mobility and tourism domain. EONA-X employs a collaborative method to improve user capabilities thereby creating novel business opportunities across the ecosystem. Overall, EONA-X is aligned with the common European mobility data space strategy. Besides, prior studies (Larrinaga, 2022; Mügge et al., 2023), employed the eclipse data space connector for secure peer-to-peer data exchange from different sources as it eliminates the need for a governance intermediary when data is exchanged among participants.

Such data ecosystems can allow data owners and data producers to incentivize their data minimizing power concentration by multinational corporations. An approach that supports fairness, trust and transparency that facilitates secure data flows through a harmonized, open data ecosystem built around strong regulations and policies such as the European Data Governance Act and the Data Act is needed to support discoverability and access to data (Montero-Pascual et al., 2023). To this end fine-grained control and regulatory efforts are needed to ensure data security and privacy when data is shared across different borders (Lohmöller et al., 2022). Also, data owners are not adequately rewarded for the value of their data that is being exploited by multi-national corporations. Additionally in smart cities data exchange enables increased efficiency of solutions and offers prospect for new business models and services (Stafford, Novacevski, Pretorius, & Rogers, 2024). However, data can only enable intelligent mobility services if there is trust in the data and if the data that is being produced, processed, shared, and stored has the appropriate safety measure. Therefore, data protection and control are paramount (Lohmöller et al., 2022). According to the literature (Frick, 2023), the significance of data sovereignty in smart cities can be summaries as shown in Table 1.

Accordingly, data sovereignty is an important requirement in smart cities (as seen in Table 1), as it grants individuals with efficient control on how to share and with whom the data to be shared with (Firdausy, Silva, Van Sinderen, & Iacob, 2022). This entails that the mo-

bility data owners and mobility data providers can specify terms and conditions for the use and sharing of their data. However, existing mobility services applications do not adequately support the data sovereignty of individuals, as such the blocking of data sharing is the safest means to maintain data sovereignty in smart cities.

4.4. Technical & non-technical requirements for achieving data sovereignty in smart cities

Data sovereignty is an evolving domain influenced by different legal frameworks, technological advancements, and geopolitical factors that still remains an ongoing challenge for individuals, organizations, and policymakers in the smart cities (Bowen & Hinze, 2022). Accordingly, this section discusses technical and non-technical requirements confronting data sovereignty from individuals’ perspectives in improving intelligent mobility services in smart cities. The identified technical and non-technical requirements are summarized in Fig. 3.

Fig. 3 illustrates the identified technical and non-technical requirements needed in realizing data sovereignty for intelligent mobility services in smart cities. Each of which are discussed below.

4.4.1. Technical requirements for achieving data sovereignty in smart cities

- a. Effective Usage Control-for data sovereignty to be effectively achieved, access and usage control is highly important to achieve intelligent mobility services. However, efficiently achieving usage control within the complete data lifecycle is technically difficult to realize in smart cities. Likewise, it is still difficult for data owners and data providers to achieve access control within the entire data processing process after the data has been shared with data users and data consumers. Thus, data access and usage control cannot be fully guaranteed even if security has been implemented in the data ecosystem. This is because the data will undoubtedly be shared and used in external digital systems or other application such as to intelligent mobility services that do not deploy any usage control implementation (Altendeitering et al., 2022).
- b. Need for Defining User Roles- there is need to specify user roles to ensure that only authorized users access data used in intelligent mobility services. For effective data governance, several user roles have need to be defined such as data steward or data owners, etc. in smart cities. Thus, there is need for common definition of user roles which are usually specified in the data usage and access control agreements in smart cities (Altendeitering et al., 2022).
- c. Need for Authentication and Authorization Enforcement- achieving data sovereign not only involves restrict access to the data, but also involves defining authentication and authorization schemes such as Keycloak systems (Altendeitering et al., 2022), which offers user

Table 1
Significance of data sovereignty in smart cities.

Key areas	Description
Data ownership and control	Data sovereignty aids individuals and businesses to retain ownership and control over their data in smart cities. Thus, ensuring that they have the authority to specify how their data is exploited, shared, and saved when they use intelligent mobility services.
Data security and privacy	Data sovereignty contributes to ensuring data security and safeguarding individuals’ privacy in smart cities. Thereby enabling legal protections and digital safety for the jurisdiction where individuals reside, thereby minimizing the risk of data breaches or illegal access when they use intelligent mobility services.
Data compliance	Regions, countries, and cities around the world have different law, regulations, and policies related to data privacy and protection. As such data sovereignty enables mobility service providers to comply with these rules by keeping individuals’ data within a specified jurisdictional boundary that is in line with relevant laws in smart cities.
Data transparency and trust	Data sovereignty can promote transparency and trust especially between data owners, data producers, data users, data consumers, data brokers, data intermediaries, and third parties that handle data in smart cities. Thus, ensuring that shared data is subject to a legal polices and accountability schemes which fosters responsible data management process across the data ecosystem in smart cities.
Promotes national interests	Data sovereignty primarily protects the interests of nationals, such as economic state, national security, etc. in smart cities. This is accomplished by aiding governments to exercise control over their sensitive data assets by preventing the unauthorized access, exploitation or use, and also support local businesses (such as mobility service providers), to developed innovative data driven services for citizens who use the mobility service provided.
Data geo-localization	Data sovereignty can promote data localization, which ensures that mobility related data is stored within the boundaries or borders of a specific country or region. This brings about investment in technological infrastructure needed for the initialization of local/national data centers which also contributes to new job creation for people involved in providing intelligent mobility services.

Fig. 3. Technical & non-technical requirements in realizing data sovereignty in smart cities.

management, strong authentication, fine-grained authorization in intelligent mobility services.

- d. Need for a Secure Environment- data sovereignty cannot be attained if the authentication and encryption mechanisms in the data ecosystem is not fully operational within intelligent mobility services. As this can impact mutual trust among the collaborating participants using the mobility application (Boye et al., 2023). Consequently, there is a need to use trusted platform modules and further enforce system security by employing encryption of all data, integrity-protected logging, safeguard against accidental misuse by admin users, use of certification and a trusted connector, etc. in smart cities (Altendeitering et al., 2022).
- e. Data Quality Prerequisite-The need for initial data cleaning and formatting is required to improve the quality of the data to be shared that is used by intelligent mobility services. Thus, data quality is important as it is vital to ensure high quality data is available to achieve intelligent mobility services. This ensures that the shared data can be easily processed and used by the external parties in smart cities (Altendeitering et al., 2022).
- f. Need for Standardization- to facilitate data exchange, there is need to develop standardized data models (Mügge et al., 2023). Also, the standardization of data models and APIs is a key determinant for scaling cross businesses which is needed for data exchange which is independent and not vendor locked to any application such as intelligent mobility services (Anthony Jnr, 2024b).
- g. Reduce Performance-when data is to be shared especially via the data ecosystem, the creation of additional steps that support data sovereignty may possibly lead to reduced performance and a higher latency in mobility applications. Evidence from literature (Altendeitering et al., 2022), mentioned that the performance can be better improved by gradually transferring small volumes of data. However, platforms deployed to support intelligent mobility services generates big data and this could cause some challenges (Altendeitering et al., 2022).
- h. Adequate Support for Legacy Technologies- findings from the literature argued that deploying data sovereignty systems are still in their infancy as such it is challenging to connect with existing technologies since issues related to data ownership is not supported in legacy technologies due to incompatible components across intelligent mobility services. Most legacy technologies are not interoperable using APIs, thus automated data acquisition, data integration, and data sharing is still not fully feasible among different backend systems used by mobility service providers (Altendeitering et al., 2022; Bokolo, 2023a).

4.4.2. Non-technical requirements for achieving data sovereignty in smart cities

- a. Adequate Domain Knowledge-evidence from prior studies highlighted that data owners and data providers face difficulty in resolving mismatches in data schema due to limited domain knowledge on data management in smart cities. Therefore, this has impacted individuals to ensure reproducibility and noticing errors in their datasets to identify wrong formatting, data errors, etc. (Altendeitering et al., 2022). Hence, there is need for the provision of support that offers training for individuals who use intelligent mobility services.
- b. Need for a Trusted Mechanism- The use of data exchange agreements that are legally and technically enforceable (Dalmolen et al., 2019), may be employed as the means for data owners and data producers to gain the required level of trust that is needed to nudge individuals to share their data to support intelligent mobility services in smart cities.
- c. Adequate Monetization Schemes- as data sharing is necessary to provide improved operational services by businesses such as mobility service providers, etc. (Jnr, 2024a). Data should certainly be monetized so that individuals can decide how their data are shared, traded, and used (Calzada, 2021). However, the lack of fair and transparent incentivization for individuals based on their data shared will negate individuals to participate in the data sharing services (Lauf et al., 2022).
- d. Need for Certification Authorities - Due to data privacy issues faced when data is shared most individuals are hesitant to share data to avoid risk. Thus, there is need to use the same terms and conditions issued by an independent trustee (such as certification authorities as independent trustee), to increase the level of trust between data owners, data providers, data consumers, data users, and other actors when sharing data to be used by intelligent mobility services (Altendeitering et al., 2022).

4.5. Data-driven intelligent mobility services in smart cities

Smart cities aim to make communities more sustainable, liveable, and equitable (Foth et al., 2021; Guenduez et al., 2024). In regions such as in Europe and in North American smart city initiatives are being implemented with many cities deploying digital technologies to improve the quality of life of citizens and also improve the environmental and economic state of their communities (Anthony Jnr, 2022; Bokolo, 2023a). Due to the use of these digital technologies and wide range of gadgets such as smartphones, sensors, smart meters, actuators, etc. in smart cities huge amounts of data that provide social and

economic value for businesses and government are generated from individuals (Dimitrijević, 2023). These data generated by individuals or produced by devices or systems deployed in smart cities includes for example citizens statistics, research data, weather data, geospatial information, etc. (Ducuing, Benmayor, & Dheu, 2022). The availability and access to high quality data is important for the provision of novel mobility applications and services, intelligent mobility services in smart cities and it's also a highly valuable asset for businesses such as public transportation companies (Altendeitering et al., 2022; Pretzsch, Drees, & Rittershaus, 2022). Therefore, the sharing and exchange of data from individuals and public transportation companies is an essential for digitization and the growth of the data economy (Altendeitering et al., 2022).

But currently, data produced in smart cities are being controlled and managed by multi-national corporations (Calzada, 2019). But the sharing of data in smart cities is faced with issues related to data governance, ownership, traceability, and access control management (Altendeitering et al., 2022). At the moment in smart cities individuals as data owners and data producers are often not at ease when they share their data. Even though contractual agreements which specifies how shared data will be utilized are signed by data consumers and data owners. This is because the individual is never certain of how and for what purpose the data shared will in reality be used, and there is also an issue of individuals losing control of their data as it is particularly challenging to ensure trust (Altendeitering et al., 2022). To this end, in smart cities there is need for data ecosystem to protect personal privacy via significant legislative acts that consider national and public security, while promoting sustainable and smart urban development (Dimitrijević, 2023). Likewise, it is important to consider data usage and access control approaches employed especially by businesses that collects, stores, and analyzes data of individuals who use digital platforms such as mobility service applications (Lai & Cole, 2023; Anthony Jr, 2023a).

Furthermore, public transportation service providers use cloud infrastructure where they duplicate and move data across data centers, which may be located in different regions to improve service performance and resource utilization. This process of data migration could possibly result to security and privacy breach (Esposito et al., 2018). Hence, while smart cities can give benefits, it is necessary to ensure that data collection, sharing, and usage is carried out by considering the digital rights of individuals especially since it pertains to the security and privacy of individuals (Dimitrijević, 2023). In improving the life of citizens in smart cities, the deployment of peer-to-peer mechanisms is needed to help individuals control, govern, and manage their data. This will help to tackle digital divide thereby enhancing individuals digital right to claim autonomy and ownership of their data (Calzada, 2021).

4.6. Data governance of intelligent mobility services in smart cities

In governing the data that is to be shared for intelligent mobility services in smart cities there are key actors that are involved as seen in Fig. 4. The actors include the individual as data owners and data producers which provides the collected data (Gao, 2021). Another actor are the companies (e.g. mobility service providers, public transportation companies, etc.), which process the shared the information or data inputs from the individuals, and presently controls the use of the collected data (Anthony Jnr, 2023c). Additional actors comprise of data consumers, data users, and third parties (data brokers, data intermediaries, digital platforms, identity services providers) who utilizes the processed data (Gao, 2021). Also, there are external actors such as certification authorities and the state, which regulates and monitors the use of the shared data via polices such as GDPR in Europe by companies which processes data and actors (data consumers, data users, and third parties) who exploits available data (Anthony Jnr, 2022). Thus, to govern the flow of data in Europe, the EU employs a diverged approach. Where, non-personal data of individuals are suggested to freely flow, whereas the cross-border flow of personal data is subjected to the rigor-

Fig. 4. Actors involved in data governance of intelligent mobility services.

ous restriction based on the GDPR, especially from countries outside the EU and within international organizations. Due to the high accordance costs and potential legal challenges associated with GDPR, it has proven to be challenging specifically for the small and medium sized enterprises and some US based websites have restricted access to individuals residing in Europe (Gao, 2021).

Therefore, to effectively govern data sharing for intelligent mobility services in data ecosystems within smart cities there is need for a practical enforceable data usage and control schemes which offers data subjects (data owners and data producers), ownership rights to manage their data, while requiring impermeable system restrictions that supports data security. Hence data owners and data producers should always be accountable and aware of all data processing activities linked to their data (Scheider, Lauf, Möller, & Otto, 2023). These enforceable data usage and control schemes are crucial as it supports data owners and data producers for compliance checking if data processing is done in line with the mutually agreed usage terms. It also helps in tracing the datasets shared with data users and data consumers within the data ecosystem system. The deployed usage control should allow for secure data processing and analysis while usage restrictions are enforced and in place as authorized by the data owners and data producers via usage policies as standardized licenses (Scheider, Lauf, Möller, & Otto, 2023). Moreover, the data provisioning carried out at the companies needs to be enabled by organizing the data in pre-defined data models (Mügge et al., 2023), where data provisioning is the process of making data available in a usable and structured format and is necessary for business intelligence, data-driven decision making, and advanced data analytics.

4.6.1. Data control scheme for data sovereignty in smart cities

Maintaining data sovereignty by data owners and data providers stems from the processes involves in managing data sharing transactions and agreements throughout the data life-cycle. This will help to prevent the misuse of the data being shared by data owners and data providers (Dalmolen et al., 2019). To foster data sovereignty in smart cities it is required to deploy data control schemes required by the mobility platforms provided by public transportation providers and used by individuals. This includes the processes for data consumers, data users, digital platforms, identity services providers, etc. to comply with internal usage control policies (e.g. on terms-of-use, access control and exchange), in line with external policies (e.g. GDPR) (Dalmolen et al., 2019; Anthony Jnr, 2024a). This will serve as a prerequisite that fosters

Fig. 5. Developed data control scheme for data sovereignty for intelligent mobility services in smart cities.

data sovereignty for all actors involves the data ecosystem (Lauf et al., 2022).

These mechanisms span to usage policies and contract negotiations drafted by the data owners and data providers to be adhered-to by data consumers and data users who use intelligent mobility services (Mügge et al., 2023). Furthermore, individuals are at the risk of data loss or negative use of their data. In businesses data is often not easily shared to avoid losses in competitive advantages. Therefore, data owners and data providers need to effectively control their generated data and its usage. Hence, prior initiatives, such as Catena-X, proposed the deployment of usage and access policies that can be defined across the Catena-X network for all data assets (Mügge et al., 2023). This is accomplished by specifying access policies (the access of data) and usage policies (on what terms accessed data is permitted to be used). Both usage and access policies can be integrated within the data ecosystem to enable a sustainable, reliable, secure, and trusted peer-to-peer data exchange that is interoperable and decentralized (Mügge et al., 2023).

Accordingly, the application of *usage and access policies* can contribute towards data sovereignty in intelligent mobility services, when data is exchange or shared within smart cities. Moreover, to prevent loss of individual control over their data which is collected and used by public transportation providers, third parties, and government authorities. It is important to establish polices and digital contracts which are legally binding that directly administers the handling of data for the interest of individuals. The digital contracts help for binding agreements with all parties thereby regulating data collection, storage, and processing as well as access, use, and sharing in a legitimized manner that fosters trust (König, 2021). Thus, grounded on the literature (Dalmolen et al., 2019; Boye et al., 2023), Fig. 5 illustrates how to enable data owners and data producers to exercise control over their data to support intelligent mobility services in smart cities.

4.6.2. Governance control to support intelligent mobility services in smart cities

This section describes how entities exercise control over their data to support intelligent mobility services in smart cities. Based on the afore-

mentioned discussion Fig. 5 proposes a data control schemes for data sovereignty to foster trust between individuals and public transportation providers, third parties, and government authorities aims at creating a transparent accountable, and fair data sharing mechanism across the data ecosystem. For data with commercialization license, data owners or data providers offers data to interested data users or data consumers based on defined usage conditions captured in the digital data usage contract. This permits data user or data consumer with the legal right to exploit the data provided as far as he/she complies with the specified conditions and provides the payment to the data owner or data provider in return (Boye et al., 2023). The payment can either be completed by direct payment or via a payment gateway service offered by data sharing ecosystem such as data spaces. Additionally, the proposed data control schemes provide data traceability, security and privacy for all participants especially individuals to reduce fraud. As sensitive individuals' data, such as travel route history and personal information, can be aggregated and used for other illicit purposes, thus individuals should have complete control of how their data is being shared and used (Stockburger, Kokosioulis, Mukkamala, Mukkamala, & Avital, 2021).

Also, verifiable continual security monitoring and cryptographically enforceable guarantees is suggested to promote the establishment of trust between data owners/data producers and data consumers/data users, data brokers, and data intermediaries in data ecosystems (Lohmöller et al., 2022). Analogous to prior studies (Lohmöller et al., 2022; Scheider, Lauf, Möller, & Otto, 2023), this study advocates for the use of the data control schemes when developing data spaces by data owners/data producers to securely exchange datasets mainly with data consumers/data users. Also, data users and data consumers are obligated as specified in the digital data usage contract that they will not use the data for any other hidden purposes other than which was stated, and the data will not be shared with other parties except stated otherwise (Boye et al., 2023). Data are imported by data owners/data producers and is stored in a private data storage as a decentralize storage location (as a cloud services e.g. Amazon bucket S3, Nextcloud, Azure storage, google drive, etc.), to be maintained by data owners/data producers via their personalized data resource profile.

Data owners/data producers have permanent ownership and access to the data through their private data storage, where they can manage stored data independently, by establishing data subject rights and license (Scheider, Lauf, Möller, & Otto, 2023). Furthermore, data owners or data providers might want to be assured that data users and data consumers will delete all mobility related data from their personal storage after the data has been processed and exploited if specified in the contract. This help to assert that data owners and data providers are in control of their data even after it has been shared with other actors in smart cities. Lastly, the data owners and data providers have the legal ability to utilize their data in the way they choose and the guarantee that parties they share data with will ultimately respect the consented usage conditions (Boye et al., 2023).

5. Discussion, recommendations, and implication

5.1. Discussion and recommendations

Digitalization in public transportation has resulted to the emergence of data ecosystems in smart cities. But presently, there are challenges associated with the autonomy and control of data across the entities in the data ecosystems who collect, analyses, processes, share and exploit data generated by individuals (Anthony Jr, 2023a). Thus, lots of personal data are collected from individuals who have no ownership or control over how their data is being used by multi-national corporations (Tan et al., 2022). It is thus crucial to have control over the custody, ownership, and exploitation of these data to protect individual's digital assets, privacy, and identity via proper data access and usage control mechanisms that safeguards their data sovereignty. However, achieving data sovereignty still remains a challenge to be resolved in smart city environment (Esposito et al., 2018). Data sovereignty which is related to the national regulations, law, and culture of the countries where the data is collected and stored or reside. It involves the control of data flows within a national jurisdiction (Calzada, 2021). Data sovereignty thus refers to the notion that the data an entity collects, processes, and stores are subject to the country's laws and governing policies where it is physically located.

In its core, data sovereignty is concern with ensuring sensitive, private data, and safeguarding that the data remains under the control and rights of its owner. Highlighting that businesses such as mobility service providers has to process and store the private information of its users in a way that adheres with all the data privacy regulations, guidelines, and best practices of the host country (Scheider, Lauf, Möller, & Otto, 2023). Therefore, this study contributes to the development of data ecosystems for governing the sharing of data thereby promoting data sovereignty to improve intelligent mobility services in smart cities. Findings from this study is similar to results from Lauf et al. (2022) by providing recommendations for improving data sovereignty for individuals in data ecosystems for the long-term benefit of both citizens and businesses to improve urban mobility services. As suggested in the literature (Scheider, Lauf, Möller, & Otto, 2023), this article designs a data control scheme to enhance the accountability and transparency by making data easily available to different stakeholders involved in providing intelligent mobility services. The data control scheme can be leverage as a tool to share urban mobility information to foster trust, enhance transparency, improve citizens engagement, and drive effective governance. The data control scheme provides a framework that allow participants to manage data sharing to ensure an effective governance via data usage control polices in smart cities.

5.2. Theoretical and practical implications

Sovereignty can be seen as the ability to have authoritative claims and control within geographical borders (Wu, 2021; Hummel et al., 2021a). Thus, to assert and/or regain sovereignty, policies that limit

businesses in the collection, processing, use, and storage of data are becoming very prevalent in cities and communities. This is largely due to the large quantities of data generated from digital application used by citizens in the society. Thus, governments are exploring best practices on how they can assert control over data on behalf of their citizens often referred to as data sovereignty (Wu, 2021). Data sovereignty empower individuals 'capability of being solely decide the usage of their data as an economic asset (Dalmolen et al., 2019). Currently, regulations, such as the EU's GDPR, etc. are established to standardize and improve how data is shared and also to protect how data of citizens in Europe are collected, processed, used, and stored.

Primarily, data sovereignty is about protecting data and ensuring it remains under the control and autonomy of its owner within a specified country. However, the lack of enacting systems that grant citizens sovereignty over their data to execute usage control and access mechanisms has limited governing the stewardship and sharing of data in data ecosystems (Tan, Chi, & Lam, 2022; Rodrigues, Amorim, Silva, & Mendes, 2023). In the transportation sector, data sharing is not only valuable, but is also needed to provide intelligent mobility services to citizens. Therefore, this study develops data control scheme as a framework that enable users to enforce their rights at any time, trust the data sharing, and to manage access to data being shared to improve urban mobility services in smart cities. Findings from this study work offers theoretical implications to practitioners on recommendations on requirements needed to design self-governing data sharing system with emphasis on data sovereignty for intelligent mobility services in smart cities. In particular, from a practical perspective this work contributes to data ecosystem research by developing a data control scheme for data sovereignty in smart cities.

6. Conclusions

Presently, data ecosystems such as those by the mobility data space, GAIA-X, IDS, EONA-X, Catena-X, etc. aimed at supporting data sovereign for different cases. However, previous works that investigated data sovereignty from the lens of intelligent mobility services or public transportation is limited. Besides, prior studies that focused on strengthening trust between different actors by incorporating data-sharing principles to accelerate mobility services innovation in smart cities are few. Nowadays mobility data is collected from several sources and should be shared between different actors to overall improve urban mobility services. However, due to the absence of data control and ownership mechanisms and the lack of trust in public transportation/mobility service providers, individuals have concerns about loss of control and misuse of their data. Thus, there is need to design appropriate data sovereignty approaches to address these concerns and thus increase individuals' willingness to share their mobility related data. Moreover, data owners and data providers sovereignty over their own data should be catered for amidst the collection, processing, use and sharing along the data ecosystem.

Accordingly, this study contributes to current body of knowledge on data sovereignty, by specifying practices previously applied to realize data sovereignty capabilities in smart cities. In general, this study explores how entities such as businesses and especially individuals can exercise control over their data to support intelligent mobility services in smart cities. Finally, this study offers an understanding of the technical and non-technical requirements needed in realizing data sovereignty into data ecosystems for intelligent mobility services in smart cities thus creating a solid foundation for future research. Additionally, this current research is subject to the following limitations. Firstly, the developed data control scheme was not evaluated. Secondly, primary data was not collected only secondary data from the literature was employed in this article. This study only identified the technical and non-technical requirements. Conclusively, further research will be focused to collect primary data based on a qualitative case study to validate the developed data control scheme. Also, the identified technical and non-technical re-

quirements will be further evaluated using case study data from domain experts' feedback. Lastly, this study will explore how existing reference models for smart cities, transferability of solutions and interoperability can contribute to improve data sovereignty for intelligent mobility services.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Bokolo Anthony Jnr: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Sizarta Sarshar:** Writing – review & editing.

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